

8T –The Quest of Defining \hat{H}

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting in which 8T is built upon, i.e. Lorentz manifold and calculus of variation, author will aspire to define the term 'energy' which is constantly being used all over the spectra of modern physics, without any solid understanding to what is term really is nor where it comes from. Since the author has in the main equation the phenomena of "dark energy", the reasoning one has built is relied upon that equation and its meaning.

Introduction

The 8T is a new theory of variational curvature. the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy". This phenomena is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an outward time invariant acceleration from those areas as given by equation (1.2.A) and the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primordial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

The subject matter of this paper is the following. Is it possible to expand the idea of energy using variational manifolds? The term energy has been used and still is used all over the modern spectra of physics. However, no theory has been able to explain what is the idea that stands behind it. Since the main equation describes the phenomena of 'dark energy' or time invariant acceleration outward from extremum curvatures, supported by the coupling constants series, it is possible using that equation, to expand and clarify the idea of Energy. Consider the idea of a certain mapping:

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi: g &\rightarrow E \\ E &= \hat{H}\end{aligned}$$

This mapping is between the Ricci curvature and the operator of energy in Quantum mechanics. So that the main equation (1.2) now can look as the following:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}'}{\partial \mathbf{t}^2} = 0$$

If we consider outward acceleration from extremum curvatures on the manifold to the term of "energy", than energy is isomorphic to the degree of curvature. The more curved the matrix on the manifold the more energy it has and vice versa. The more flat the manifold is the less energy it contain. This idea than indicating that the manifold will aspire to reach the highest degree of flatness, indicating lowest degree of curvature overtime. That is in agreement with the idea of stationary manifold. "Energy" can also by analyzed in the context of the transformation between curvature to flatness, the manifold in the beginning was highly curved and as a result of being a part of the packet it was immediately flattened by the packet, which led to very high rate of change of curvature, which is isomorphic to energy, which manifested itself in the beginning. Once the manifold got flattened, the rate of change of curvature to time is significantly lower and aspire lower and lower value as the manifold expands. Each time net amount of curvature appearing matter is clustering toward it leading to formations of stars and galaxies. Using that construction, it is possible to construct the idea of potential energy. Potential energy is value, which describe the amount of curvature within fermion cluster. This term also include the fact that each matter unit itself is composed by Quarks, which are vanishing curvature spikes. Therefore, the potential energy can be put in rigor as the sum of two equations (1.48) and (1.49):

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \quad (1.5)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \subset \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.51)$$

Equation (1.51) meant to express the idea of a matter cluster with Bosons that propagate within it. As the subset of Bosons is larger, the more amount of matter being clustered making the potential energy higher. It is important to clarify that matter itself is only a part of the picture itself, as it has no curvature itself, but it is composed to arbitrary amounts of curvature that must vanish to keep the manifold stationary, which are two distinct elements which differ in sign, or Quarks. The total energy of the specific manifold is described by:

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i = \hat{T} + \hat{U} \quad (1.52)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Okad's Theory